

COCHLEAR IMPLANTATION – A MODERN METHOD OF HEARING RESTORATION

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Abstract: This article discusses cochlear implantation as a modern method of hearing restoration, what degrees and ages of hearing impairment are eligible for surgery, the importance of rehabilitation in pre- and post-operative stages, in what cases surgery can be performed and in what cases there are contraindications to surgery, and the importance of CI surgery in the lives of children with hearing impairments.

The Republic of Uzbekistan is rising socially, economically, and spiritually due to its independence. Through the initiatives of our country's President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, fundamental changes are being made to the education sector. Specifically, the Republic of Uzbekistan's "Law on Education" guarantees equal rights to education for everyone regardless of gender, race, nationality, language, religion, social origin, belief, personal and social status. It also stipulates that children with physical, mental, sensory, or psychological disabilities, as well as children requiring long-term treatment, receive education in state specialized educational institutions, general secondary and specialized secondary educational organizations in inclusive form, or individually at home.

Based on the Resolution PQ-4860 dated October 13, 2020, of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the system of education and upbringing of children with special educational needs," a number of opportunities were created for children with special educational needs.

Categories of Children with Hearing Impairments

Deaf children - children whose hearing ability has decreased profoundly and permanently from birth or early period, and as a result cannot master speech without special pedagogical assistance.

Hard of hearing children - children with reduced hearing that interferes with speech acquisition and verbal communication.

Late-deafened children - children who lost their hearing ability at 2-3 years of age or later, but whose speech has been preserved. For deaf and hard of

hearing children, depending on the type of defect, correction is carried out using sound amplifying devices and cochlear implant devices during their education and upbringing process. Specifically, cochlear implants are used for deaf children, while sound amplifying devices are used for hard of hearing children.

To ensure the implementation of the "Healthy Child Year" State Program approved by Resolution PQ-2133 dated February 19, 2014, of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, regulations were approved for the selection of patients for cochlear implantation operations in medical institutions in accordance with the statute on the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved by Resolution No. 18 dated January 14, 1999, of the Cabinet of Ministers. According to the regulations, the following conditions are specified for cochlear implantation: Cochlear implantation operations are performed to restore the hearing ability of persons with bilateral sensorineural hearing loss of III-IV degrees or deaf persons through stimulation of the inner ear using multi-channel electrodes. Cochlear implantation operations are performed at the Republican Specialized Pediatric Scientific-Practical Medical Center.

Cochlear implantation operations and post-operative rehabilitation measures for pediatric patients are carried out free of charge. Considering that cochlear implantation surgery gives positive results when performed before the patient child reaches 5 years of age, implants purchased with budget funds are provided free of charge to children under 5 years of age for effective use.

If parents, guardians, or sponsors of pediatric patients under 5 years of age do not wish to wait in line for cochlear implantation surgery performed with implants purchased with budget funds, they can purchase the implant themselves. For pediatric patients aged 5 and older, cochlear implantation surgery is performed at the request of parents, guardians, or sponsors and when they purchase the implant.

Regardless of age, pediatric patients who have lost their hearing ability as a result of meningitis undergo cochlear implantation surgery within six months and are provided with implants free of charge. The time when the pediatric patient lost hearing ability due to meningitis is determined based on a copy of their medical history. The implant is provided free of charge for only one ear. When a family has two or more pediatric patients under 5 years of age, to ensure the effectiveness of post-cochlear implantation rehabilitation measures, an implant is provided free of charge to only one of them in one calendar year.

Citizens not covered by these regulations, as well as foreign citizens and stateless persons, receive cochlear implantation surgery and subsequent rehabilitation measures from the Center on a paid basis, in accordance with the regulations on the Republican Specialized Pediatric Scientific-Practical Medical Center approved by Resolution No. 145 dated May 21, 2009, of the Cabinet of Ministers.

In our country, the "Zamin" Foundation is carrying out a number of effective works on cochlear implantation. On International Children's Protection Day, the "Zamin" Foundation presented an education development program for nearly five thousand students with hearing impairments in the country's specialized institutions. The project's goal is to implement new teaching methods and improve the infrastructure of boarding schools. Within the framework of the project, work is being carried out to restore students' hearing ability through surgical practice. This means that children with health problems can hear the voices of their loving mothers and caring fathers, surrounding sounds, and musical melodies, and live a full life. Partial or complete loss of hearing deprives people of an important source of information and limits the intellectual development process. In most cases, children with disabilities face a number of difficulties, one of which is the lack of opportunity to receive full education.

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